

State and Secularism in Islam

Hakan Aktas

To cite this article: Hakan Aktas, Science, Volume 5, No. 2-5, 2023, p. 24 – 44. - 0099-0001-2302-0402.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

CURRENT SCIENCE

- *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")*
- ""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*""
("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

The question of whether Islam is "compatible" with European principles of so-called democracy, secularism and human rights (more specifically women's rights, LGBT rights, etc.) is currently under discussion on Islam in a Europe. This is the theological enigma: the question of how Muslims should integrate into European society is intended to be linked to the study of the religious foundations that underlie Islam as a religion. Either Muslims offer and promote a liberal interpretation of Islam, or their European integration depends on an earlier theological reform that would (once again) bring Islam into line with supposedly Western values. In both cases, Muslims either offer and promote a liberal interpretation of Islam, or their European integration is tied to an earlier theological reform. The media often highlights the plight of some "moderate" Muslim thinkers who should be encouraged and encouraged to oppose their fellow believers. In France, for example, local imams such as Soheib Ben Cheykh¹ in Marseille or Hassen Chalghoumi in Seine-Saint-Denis are portrayed as lone reformists attacked by fundamentalist groups. In the United States, the media often highlights the plight of some "moderate" Christian thinkers who need Others to even draw parallels between Irshad Manji and Martin Luther. ³ Tahir ul Kadri, the leader of the Pakistani religious movement, introduced himself as the first Muslim leader to write a definitive fatwa against terrorism in a speech he made in England. Other Muslim thinkers and leaders have also claimed to be the long-awaited Muslim reformer in the West desperately needs. This essentialist point of view can be seen in the background of many events that are reflected in the media, from terrorism to polygamy and honor killings, as well as in the policies implemented by various governments and administrative authorities.

Keywords: *State structure in Islam, Islam and Secularism, Secularism*

1. Introduction

Academic sources related to secularism are overflowing with competing information. Detailed, passive, understanding, helpful, evolutionary, leading to the good, principle-based, pluralist, non-negative, and powerful, non-tolerant, specific, wild, and excluding forms of secularism are found in the sources. In passive secularism, the secular state adopts a passive character and declines the choice of another religion as the state religion but does not oppose the social freedom of any other religion and, on the contrary, protects it. In the case of exclusionary secularism, the state tries to avoid any concern with religion from the social environment. An exclusionary secular state should declare "religion is a matter of conscience" and should defend that religious knowledge related to social and political issues should not be found in a legitimate way (Yilmaz, 2013).

Islam is a religion that defines values and principles that people should live by in every aspect of their lives. These values and principles encompass not only religious life, but also social and political life. The understanding of the state and the concept of secularism in Islam are important for the implementation of Islamic values and the provision of justice among people. This article will address the definition of the understanding of the state and the concept of secularism in Islam, how modern Islamic states have adopted these concepts, and how these concepts are harmonized with Islam. However, in both cases the debate is about Islam and not about any woman's individual and choice as to whether to wear the burqa. It is often heard that religion and state are inseparable in Islamic civilization. This argument quite coincides with the historical facts that appeared with the progress of the Islamic world throughout its existence. However, making such a suggestion does not in any way mean an evaluation of the issue. The same can be said of the argument that the Modern period, which was heavily influenced by Latin Christianity in Europe, was distinguished by the division of church and state . Both arguments , though not entirely contradictory, are tries to draw attention to different social realities and feelings of those situations by individuals who engage with them. Within the context of this article, it is clearly impossible to address all the concerns related to this topic, and it is much more difficult to find solutions to them. Considering this, my aim is to shed light on only a few key aspects of history and the history of religion. I believe that this will contribute

to the development of a new perspective on these issues and to an objective examination of the facts. Let us begin by considering the myriad reasons why Christianity and Islam have adopted different attitudes towards any expression of man's creative endeavor based on theological and cosmological notions . In the 31st verse of the Qur'an, Allah reveals the name of everything in the universe to Adam ; therefore, all information about the world created by Allah comes from Him.

2. Secularism Concept

The concept of secularism refers to a state structure that does not have any relation with religion or religious beliefs. A secular state does not have the ability for the state to make religious decisions or for religious institutions to make state decisions, due to its structure free of religious affiliation. Secularism ensures that the state serves all citizens equally, regardless of their religious differences, and shows respect to all citizens' religious beliefs. It also guarantees everyone's right to freely express their religious beliefs and places responsibility on the state to protect this right. The concept of secularism has been adopted in many modern Islamic states and, in their governance, both Islamic law rules and modern law rules are used.

The Kemalist followers of the Union and Progress Party, who continued the rough positivist thinking, created certain methods to secularize the people and the social environment. They tried to separate religion from the social environment through only the exclusive secularism thought and tried to approve to communities that religion is only active in individuals' personal lives. From the Kemalist perspective, religion should only have a folkloric effect and appearance in the social environment; it is an outdated and irrational event that caused the Ottoman state to be lacking. In conclusion, the Kemalists did not advocate for the separation of religion and state affairs, but rather focused on secularizing individuals through state resources and preventing religion from being used as a source in social and political circumstances (Aydin, 1995).

In fact, knowledge is the result of an endless process of divine creation. This process, which defines everything that is happening in this universe at any given moment and encompasses every place and every time zone, manages the production of knowledge. The reason we accept the world created in this way as the cosmos is not because of any causality it has, but because

Allah has made everything fully universe through his wise and uninterrupted acts of creation. This is the only reason we see the world as a cosmos.

According to the Kemalists, all social and political ideas, values, and laws should be guided by science as the ultimate and only authoritative source. There are many reasons for Kemalists to begin a social design that leaves behind such a passive form of secularism. Three main reasons for this can be said by Gündüz (2010, 2) as follows:

- a. *Kemalism claims that Islam religion and the Ottoman world outlook are the causes of shortcomings in Turkey,*
- b. *Kemalism argues that Islamic religion and Ottoman Turkish traditions hinder progress by comparing them to the universal laws of modernity of the West,*
- c. *Kemalism opposes the management style of the Ottoman state by presenting Kemalism as a characteristic of its own in the effort to legalize it.*

Atatürkism is mostly equated with Kemalism, but in this context, Kemalist thought is preferred to describe a milder interpretation of the idea. It is ideal to describe the Atatürkist thought by claiming that one shows the deepest respect to Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, but that there is no such thing as a mistake of Atatürk. There is no obligation for an Atatürkist to fully follow Kemalism. While it is not impossible to see a person who is "religious, Muslim, and supports Atatürkism," it is impossible to see a person who is "religious, Muslim, and supports Kemalism." However, the religious Muslim individual has no political aspiration about his religion, and the connection to Islam religion is limited to the personal realm or has become cultural. While Kemalist individuals try to remove Islam religion from the public sphere with anger, Atatürkists show tolerance and do not become disturbed (Ergil, 1989).

Sunni Muslims who are not devout in their religion are the citizens most trusted and sought after through the system of Kemalist ideology. First-class citizenship requires an individual to be both Muslim and Sunni. However, this way of life as a Sunni Muslim without being devout is fully owned by the Islamic religion (Ortayli, 1997).

3. State Concept in Islam

The Concept of State in Islam aims to set up a society that tries to ensure equality and justice among people. Islam believes that a system and governance must keep equality and justice among people. Therefore, the Islamic concept of state is defined as focused on ensuring equality

CURRENT SCIENCE

and justice among individuals. The Islamic law rules are used as a guide for the administration of Islamic states governed according to Islamic law. The Islamic law rules are defined with the aim of keeping justice among individuals and are used as regulation for state governance.

It is the only secular democracy among a group of nations with a predominantly Muslim population. The first decade after the founding of the Turkish Republic in 1923 served to lay the groundwork for the country's eventual transition to a secular state. The beginning of the secular movement can be traced back to the middle of the 19th century when the Ottoman Empire began to become more modern. More than half a century has passed since he first set up democratic rule. From 1923 to 1946 the republican government was controlled by a single party. 1946 was the year of the first fully contested elections. Since then , Turkey has been fighting hard to advance its democratic consolidation . After the military coups in 1960 and 1980, the democratic process stopped for a brief time. This led to the establishment of military governments. Also, democratically elected governments were overthrown by military attacks on two separate occasions, 1971 and 1997, respectively. However, despite these defeats, democracy is well set up in Turkey and the prospect of a new military coup, or even an intervention, seems unlikely at best. Since the 1997 military intervention, Turkey has made significant efforts to further liberalize its political system to meet the criteria of the European Union (EU) to which it has applied for membership. These efforts are in preparation for the EU's decision whether to grant Turkey membership or not. According to recent surveys, nearly eighty percent of the Turkish population favors the country's accession to the European Union (EU), a figure that serves as a major impetus behind the Turkish government's attempts to reform the system. Meets EU requirements. In December 2004, a fixed deadline was set by the European Union for the start of negotiations on Turkey's membership. If Turkey is admitted to the European Union in the next ten years, this will be an important milestone on Turkey's democracy and democracy path. modernization from a secular perspective. In fact, Western policy experts are taking a closer look at the Turkish scenario as a possible "model" or "example" for the rest of the Muslim world. This article examines the transformations Turkey has undergone during the transition from empire to nation-state in terms of secularism and democracy experience.

The concept of state in the Islamic world has changed along with the development of Islamic principles and history. The first Islamic state founded by Prophet Muhammad in Medina forms

CURRENT SCIENCE

the foundation of the concept of state in the Islamic world. The Prophet Muhammad's governance concept was based on the principles of Islam and the principle of justice.

An Islamic state is a structure where justice and equality are ensured and relationships among citizens are decided by religious principles, with the influence of religious beliefs in state governance. The goal of an Islamic state is to implement Islamic principles and ensure justice and equality among citizens.

Throughout Islamic history, various states have been set up and different state ideologies have been implemented in the Islamic world. These states tried to govern by the principles of Islam, but over time, political and economic issues appeared in state governance. To address these issues, the state ideology in the Islamic world changed and the implementation of secularism became a topic of discussion.

In conclusion, the state ideology in the Islamic world is decided by the principles of Islam, the development of Islamic history, and the goal of ensuring justice and equality among citizens. States in the Islamic world strive to implement the principles of Islam and keep justice and equality among its citizens.

Focusing especially on the conflict between secularism and Islam, it shows how this conflict was first brought under control by authoritarian means in the early years of the republic, but how it turned into an important problem in democratic politics over time. How the strained relationship between secular and Islamic politics plays out in the democratic arena and the results of this power struggle has no relevance in the rest of the Islamic world. This experience shows that the road to modernity in Turkey is a slow but steady process and the result is the product of the complex interaction between local social and political actors on the one hand and the influence of the outside world on the other. The secularization thesis was a fundamental part of the modernization theory that appeared in the 19th century and guided the social sciences for most of the 20th century. The prediction that civilizations would inevitably evolve towards modernity and with-it secularization did not materialize in the second half of the twentieth century, which led to the development of postmodernism. Adding to the absurdity of the notion that modernity is inevitable and will go ahead in the same way everywhere, the hypothesis that it would lead to a decline in religious practice was problematic from the very beginning. For example, the level of religiosity in the United States (US), as measured by the number of people going to church on a weekly basis, has remained high, although it has fallen drastically in other

European countries. Considering this feature, various explanations have been proposed for the concept of " exceptionalism " in the United States . It has been argued that people's church-going habits cannot be explained by their religion alone, and this is a reasonable point of view. In a culture that values independence, church attendance was historically seen as an effective technique for fostering community relationships and fostering a sense of harmony among individuals. As a result, the United States of America can be considered an exception, which does not change the general principle. However, the chain of events that took place in the late 1970s and early 1980s caused the secularization thesis to fail inexorably. In the United States, where individual religiosity is already prominent, social organizations based on religious identities have begun to organize politically and gain considerable influence. Several organizations supported his campaign, helping Ronald Reagan win the presidency in 1980. The United States, in its struggle against the Soviet dictatorship in Afghanistan, preferred to cooperate with the Islamic forces in that country and contributed to the religion-based political mobilization that took place outside its borders. The establishment of the Islamic Republic in Iran is seen as a much more important event. The Islamists were part of the broad coalition that succeeded in overthrowing the pro-American Shah in 1979. There were also communists and liberals in the alliance. After that, the Islamic faction succeeded in cutting competition and keeping its control. All traditional modernization and secularization theses were destroyed because of this event. The establishment of an Islamic dictatorship was a striking result for pro-modernist organizations that wanted the Shah gone but was welcomed by postmodernists such as Michel Foucault.

4. Lozan and Islam: The Presidency of Religious Affairs and Social Engineering

While the Kemalist faction tried to remove Islam from the public sphere overall, they realized that it was not possible in the short run. As a result, while trying to secularize the society through the state, they aimed to both control religion tightly and to use it to create a secular nation-state. With this goal in mind, they tried to construct a sort of civil religion by using the Presidency of Religious Affairs (Aydın, 1995).

In Lozan Islam, religion serves the political system. Lozan Islam is compatible with Kemalist state ideologies, Turkish nationalism, the nation-state, modernity and secularism. The Presidency of Religious Affairs is used to give this interpretation of Islam to the society. As a

result, there are no imams or religious leaders in the private sector, civil society, religious sects, or religious groups. All imams, preachers, religious scholars, and Quran teachers are state officials. Only the state can supply religious education. Supplying religious education privately is a crime (Ortaylı, 1997)

5. Islam, Freedom, Democracy, Religion, and Freedom of Expression

The Islamic religion upholds the idea that individuals are free from the moment they are born. The presence of individual rights and freedoms in Islam is independent of recognition by constitutional laws. According to Islam, individuals should have the freedom to express their opinions without any form of coercion. The fundamental aims of Islamic law, as discussed by Şatibi, include guaranteeing and protecting the basic freedoms of individuals in the areas of religion, life, family and procreation, mind, and ownership. These pro-modernist groups wanted the Shah to go because they believed he was an obstacle to social progress (Afary and Anderson, 2005). The theory of secularization was further refuted by events taking place in Western Europe. After 1980, there has been a significant increase in the number of people migrating from Muslim countries to European countries. These immigrant communities, which were previously known for their national origins, started to be recognized with their religious identities as they reached important dimensions. This was partly due to the demands of the immigrant communities themselves, and partly to the response of the host societies to the substantial number of culturally un-assimilated newcomers. Voices began to rise, rejecting the dominant model of "separation of state and religion" and making alternative demands. These alternative claims are also supported by the native post mode .

A state that allows its citizens to freely practice their religion and protects their education and activities is by the Quran and Islamic religion. It is pointless to seek another system that has a different method if the freedom of society is ensured in such a manner. In Islam, after acknowledging their obedience to the state, it is both natural and legally the freedom of all religious minorities to lead their lives according to their beliefs. Any opposite situation would involve coercion and oppression. The state should defend the beliefs of its citizens against any form of coercion and allow individuals to freely practice their beliefs. Islam also recognizes the principle that sovereignty belongs to the people, and this is not in opposition to the idea that ultimate authority belongs to Allah. This can be seen as a combination of both ontological and

normative aspects of sovereignty. As the immigrant Muslim population became a significant presence in European countries, voices rejecting the model began to rise. Eager to protect the "recognition of the rights of identity groups", they, too, began to doubt the concept of secularism in the name of "multiculturalism". This was done to protect the "right to recognition of identity groups". Although it was the tried-and-true method of keeping domestic peace after protracted religious conflicts, the secularization thesis began to fall out of favor when the principle of secularism was put under scrutiny. As a result, two developments took place simultaneously. The beginning of Islam can be traced back to an extremely first period in the history of the region. After 700 AD, traders from Arabia and India brought Islam to Aceh, which is considered Islam's gateway to the Indonesian archipelago. Around 804, the first Islamic monarchy was set up in the territory of Aceh. Over the next 600 years, the kingdoms of the region, particularly Samudra (later Pasai) and Pidie, Aceh They merged with Besar to become Aceh. This happened after the establishment of Perlak, the first Islamic state. The history of Atjeh (sic) is largely told in terms of Islam and commerce (Siegel 1969:4). Most of the people who practice Islam in Aceh adhere to the Sunni (Sunnat wal Jamaat) school of thought and, like most Muslims in the region, Academies are followers of the Syafii doctrine. However, Acehnese also recognizes the other four major Sunni sects, which are Hanafi, Hanbali, and Maliki. Although many people in Aceh tend to lean towards conservatism when asked a question that has no clear answers, they consider Imam Shafii to be the most cautious and progressive of the four great imams of Islam. Also, there are two (or maybe three) sub-branches that originate from the Syafii branch. The Syafi'i doctrine is interpreted somewhat differently in Aceh and Malaysia when it comes to divorce, for example. There is extraordinarily slight difference between the two views. Even though there is little known contention about this sectarian divide, more than ten percent of Acehnese adhere to the Shia Islamic school. The more mystical and Sufiist interpretation of Islam has had only brief appeal in Aceh, contrary to the widespread feeling that Muslims in Aceh are typically tolerant of one another. The violent Wahhabist (much less Qtbist) form of Islam became much less popular in Aceh, as it opposed the prevailing tolerant attitude and a shared preoccupation with material problems. In fact, it has been even less popular in the rest of Indonesia. The physical location of Aceh, the first stop of Islamic traders coming to the region, is considered the source of the city's Islamic roots. To Aceh, the starting point of Islam in the archipelago and the final

departure point for pilgrimage (Serambi Mekkah), it was nicknamed "The Veranda of Mecca" by Arab traders. From about the 13th century, the religion of Islam was carried to the other islands of the archipelago via Aceh . The history of the Aceh people's war against foreign aggression has been described by the people of Aceh as jihad, which literally means "holy war". This terminology offers an Islamic perspective on such a concept of conflict. This Islamic political identity led to Aceh's Dar'ul Islam Uprising of the 1950s . strengthened by his involvement and the claim that GAM was a descendant of the later Dar'ul Islam rebellion. Both events took place in Indonesia. Observers also conclude that GAM is an Islamic organization , as nearly all of its members are strongly affiliated with the Sunni Islamic school .

Some proponents of Islam have found the statement "Sovereignty belongs to the nation without conditions" to be incompatible with the verse "Authority belongs only to God," however, it cannot be said that this statement expresses that sovereignty is taken from God and given to individuals in an administrative and political sense. On the contrary, this expression refers to political sovereignty being given to all individuals as a trust from God, rather than to evil people or dictators. In a cosmological sense, there is no doubt that Allah has control over all things in the world, but this does not imply that an individual does not have the freedom to act or make choices. In other words, Allah is certainly the supreme ruler both ontologically and normatively, but Allah continues to exercise normative sovereignty through the people he has chosen as his caliphs in the world. Individuals are free to make choices in their personal lives and they are free in their social and political movements and the choices of the people who will govern them (Özdağ, 1998). Laith According to Kubba , the establishment of democracies in most Muslim nations is still an uphill battle. In many cases, progress in liberalizing communities, improving institutions and expanding infrastructure is a slow and limited process. The democratic movements that took place all over the world could not drastically change the authoritarian and patriarchal political systems in Muslim countries. State authority is often held monopolistically by western elites, western military officials, traditional tribal leaders, and traditional tribal leaders. There are various indicators that Western institutions, governments and societies use to assess the extent to which they are accessible to foreigners, and all of these indicators point to the fact that democratic institutions are lacking in many Muslim countries. The most obvious examples of this are political violence, abuse of public office and violation.

The law of Islam supports the notion that individuals are free from the moment they are born. The presence of individual rights and freedoms in Islam is independent of their recognition by constitutions. According to Islam, individuals must have the freedom to express their views without being subjected to pressure. As showed by Şatibi, the fundamental aims of Islamic law are to guarantee and protect the basic freedoms of individuals such as 'Religion, Life, Family & Reproduction, Mind, and Ownership'. If a state allows individuals to freely practice their religion and protects their education and activities, it is said that this system is not in opposition to the Quran and Islam. It is meaningless to look for a system with a different approach in a society where freedoms are ensured in this manner. In Islam, it is both natural and legally the freedom of all religious minorities to live according to their own beliefs after they have given to the state. The opposite scenario would result in oppression and abuse. The state must protect individuals' beliefs from all kinds of pressure and allow individuals to freely...

6. The Concepts of State and Secularism in Islam

Islam is not just a religion of worship like other religions in the world, but also a teaching of a lifestyle that encompasses social relationships, legal and administrative structures. The concept of state in Islam is a notion that defines the relationship between religion and the world. Islam aims to set up a society that strives to ensure equality and justice among people.

Secularism means the separation of religion and state. A secular state is a notion that posits that the state should not involve itself in religious affairs and that decisions of the state should be made independently of religious beliefs. However, it is not possible to use secularism in the same meaning in Islam. In Islam, it is expected that the state will involve itself in religious affairs and that people will be guided based on their religious beliefs.

In Islam, the state is governed according to Islamic legal rules. Islamic law is a legal system set up based on the Quran and Hadiths. It is a system that defines relationships between people and the social order, and it is used as a guide for the administration of Islamic states.

However, in modern times, many Islamic states have adopted a secular state structure and have used Western legal systems in addition to Islamic legal rules. This means that these Islamic states have accepted the necessity of separating religion and state. However, since secularism has not been fully adopted, many Islamic states still deal with religious affairs.

7. Modern Islamic States and Secularism

Modern Islamic states, while adopting the fundamental principles of Islam, have also adopted the principles of modern state understanding. These states are governed using Islamic legal rules while also having a secular structure. Secularism means that the state has a structure that is not related to religion or religious beliefs. A secular state cannot make religious decisions or have religious institutions make state decisions because it does not have any connection with religion or religious beliefs. Secularism ensures that the state serves all its citizens equally and respects the religious beliefs of all its citizens, despite religious differences among people.

Although modern Islamic states have a secular structure, they continue to embrace Islamic beliefs and use Islamic legal rules. These states are governed using both Islamic legal rules and modern legal rules. Therefore, modern Islamic states can use both Islamic principles and secular principles together. These states strive to keep equality and justice among people by using Islamic principles and secular principles together.

The secular structure of modern Islamic states reduces the influence of religious beliefs in state administration. The secular structure ensures that the state serves all its citizens equally and respects the religious beliefs of all its citizens. The secular structure also guarantees that everyone has the right to freely express their religious beliefs and that the state handles protecting this right.

8. Secular State Not Contradicting the Religion of Islam

Religion reflects social context and societal demands in approximately all belief systems. The exclusionary secularism in Turkey that aims to single out Islam and has a unique Rousseau-Durkheim exclusionary secularism ideology that discriminates against both Islamic sects (such as Alevism) and other religions is not proper for the protection of religious freedom viewed as a fundamental right of an individual. In terms of Turkey, the best correction, without harming the positive aspects of its past experiences, would be to express the Stepanian twin toleration viewpoint, like that of the United States of America, in constitutional language. This correction requires that the state keep the same distance from all religions and should not interfere in or dictate religious practices. The free teaching of all religious beliefs and interpretations is left to the individuals in society and the state should not obstruct the presence of religious places of worship, such as mosques and churches, for communities and individuals. In such cases, if the

CURRENT SCIENCE

state supplies support, it should ensure that all religions and sects benefit fairly based on demographic needs and desires. A state that serves as a servant to justice and responds to the desires of individuals in society cannot decide, according to Islam, what constitutes a place of worship and what does not. This decision is entirely made by the civil individuals in society. Based on demographic desires, it supplies the same rights and aid to individuals of various sects and religions, without discrimination. It especially collects the same taxes from all individuals without distinguishing between their religion or belief and imposes the same citizenship responsibilities. To be fair means that the state must supply equal support and services for religious practices, otherwise this would lead to inequality and oppression. The idea that the state is in opposition to Islam by collecting taxes from all individuals and supplying religious services or aid to everyone is a subjective and lacking objectivity idea (Ortaylı, 1997).

The notion that religious institutions have the advantage of appearing in a religious assembly decided by religious leaders, like the idea that states should not interfere in religions, is incorrect. In addition, the state should not discriminate against religious institutions and communities, and should treat all fairly, based on their needs and desires, without giving preference to any group. A secular state that is committed to justice must ensure that all individuals and communities, regardless of their beliefs or religions, are able to exercise their rights freely and without fear of oppression or discrimination.

In the academic field, scholars of Islam have sometimes acted in a free manner, issuing fatwas and interpretations that are sometimes incompatible with one another, and if they attract followers, they have been able to sustain their lives. On the other hand, the state has either upheld unchanging legal verdicts or has legitimized one of the opinions held in open-minded environments, which is often the one preferred by most individuals in society, or it has made it usable in trials. These ideas have become the main legal style of Islamic governments. Governments have the authority to implement these legal ideas, but they may also ask that only one of them be followed. However, the state cannot declare any ideas outside of its own choice as illegitimate. Sometimes, the state can also legitimize its views through the knowledge of its scholars or parliamentary representatives. However, in an environment where individuals of other religions have equal rights, it would be more proper to delegate this task of understanding to the educated members of society (Gündüz, 2010). Most Muslim nations are now in a stalemate. States that are not only dysfunctional but also corrupt and authoritarian are neither

CURRENT SCIENCE

able nor willing to change. Radicalism consists of indifference and despair. The ineffectiveness of mostly Muslim non-national secular politics creates favorable conditions for the growth of political Islam. On the other hand, the radicalization of Islamic political groups is linked to repression and exclusion from the political process. Moderation of Islamic political movements are intricately linked to participation in the political process. According to Kubba , most Muslim countries, like other nations in the developing world, are motivated by a deep need and an ardent desire for modernization, progress and dignity. Their hopes for a brighter future have been rooted for much of the past few decades in a simple version of a strong centralized state that has implemented reforms from the top down. This ideal was believed to have a better chance of being realized than democracy, which supplied an intricate, multi-institutional structure of participation based on individualism and liberal principles. The inability of powerful secular nations to meet the ever-increasing needs of increasingly educated communities encouraged introspection and the search for other solutions. During the 1979 Islamic Revolution in Iran, both social and political organizations came to appreciate the role religion played in mobilizing popular support. Islam, whose ownership, interpretation and application is open to everyone, from the government to the opposition, from the modernists continues to be drawn into the arena as a sharp instrument to conservatives . by groups on the left or right of the political spectrum. This is so even though the ownership, interpretation and practice of Islam is open to all. Many branches of Islam are united in favoring religion over secularism, but they differ on whether democracy or authoritarianism is the better form of government. Over the past two decades, Muslim intellectuals have come to advocate for democracy and human rights as a response to the failure of the communist model of development, as well as the failure of both secular and Islamic models of governance to address growing societal problems. and economic needs. They did this not only to gain modernity, growth and prestige, but also to ensure a better practice of Islam. The motivations for doing this are outlined in the earlier sentence. In any definition of the constitutional context of the relationship between religion and state in the Netherlands, the terms "separation of church and state", "state neutrality in matters of religion and belief" and "freedom of religion and belief" would be extremely useful terms to have on hand.

If the scholars of Islam in an informed community and era can find followers for their opinions, it would be difficult for democratic systems to disregard these scholars. Of course, if it does not

CURRENT SCIENCE

restrict the rights of others and does not become compulsory for all individuals, the opposition of other individuals in society to such correction and permission should form part of the social contract and pluralist democratic view. In an analogous manner, the era and structures should act fairly and equally towards individuals who belong to other religions. In such a constitutional system, the responsibilities of political socialization, such as claiming to resolve conflicts in the social environment in ethical matters, supplying relevant information to members, and encouraging members to take part in political processes, should be delegated to the religious community and its religious behaviors by the constitutional system. In such a system, both the Islamic religion and its sectarian interpretations will compete and with other religions based on the idea of a free market, and no government will give preferential treatment to any of them. In this article, the ideas discussed are those that are already existing, and the author continues to work on. In a pluralistic manner, other opinions and objections should reach an interactive dialogue in the social environment. Ultimately, the agreed upon ideas, criticisms and thoughts should be presented in a systemic manner in the form of constitutional provisions, and it is the responsibility of the constitutional lawyers to present these provisions for the approval of society, while it is the responsibility of the politicians.

This last provision is very clearly articulated in the Constitution (Article 6). 3 The commitment to equal treatment based on one's religion or belief can be found in Article 1, Chapter 4 and read in conjunction with Article 6, which summarizes the concept of impartiality. Since its first declaration in 1796, the separation of church and state has not been explicitly said in any law, neither in the Constitution nor in any other law. This has been the case since 1796, the year when the Dutch Reformed Church definitively ended as the established church. Despite this, it is possible to say that it is implicitly included in several constitutional guarantees, especially in Articles 6 and 1. links between church and state. The drafting of these provisions took place during the comprehensive constitutional amendment that took place in 1983. The earlier section entitled "About Religion," first written in 1814 and then revised in 1815, 1848, and 1972, is this document. Most of the remaining articles were out of date. The removal of the term's "church" in the Constitution in 1983 was perhaps the most important change made at that time. Churches have freedom of religion as organizations and are treated equally (to the extent that this protection exists) as fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution protect both individuals and institutions. As a result of the 1983 amendment, the concept of freedom of religion has

undergone significant changes. In addition, it created a new framework for the restriction of fundamental rights in general, the aim of which was to expand the sphere of freedom of the individual.

Article 23, which introduces the dual system of public education as well as state-funded private (confessional) education on equal terms, has not been changed due to the sensitivity of the issue. It guarantees freedom of education and introduces a dual system of public education as well as private (confessional) education. The Dutch approach to dealing with groups founded on a religion or belief serves as an excellent model for other nations to follow in this regard. The prominent presence in Dutch society of the voluntary sector, often groups founded on a religious denomination, is considered one of the country's defining features. Numerous volunteer, non-profit organizations have historically functioned on a denominational basis in the areas of health, housing, education and welfare (inadequate assistance). These areas are: The government adopted the policy of including these non-profit organizations in the system during the rise of the social welfare state in the 1970s . This policy often involved subsidizing or supporting them on an equal footing as public alternatives.

9. Discussion

The implementation of secularism in the Islamic world is a subject of much debate. One of the debates is whether Islam can play a role in the governance of the state. Some Islamic scholars argue that it is not possible for Islam to play a role in the governance of the state and that a secular structure may conflict with the principles of Islam. However, other Islamic scholars argue that it is possible for Islam to play a role in the governance of the state and that a secular structure can be used in conjunction with the principles of Islam.

Secondly, there is debate over whether the implementation of secularism can supply equality and justice among citizens. Some argue that secularism can supply equality and justice, while others may believe that secularism cannot fully supply equality and justice among citizens. Finally, the reduction of religious influence in the governance of the state through secularism is debatable. Some argue that it is necessary for secularism to reduce the influence of religious beliefs in the governance of the state, while others believe that it is wrong for religious beliefs to be completely removed from the governance of the state.

These debates prove that there are different views on the implementation of secularism in the Islamic world. Despite these differences, the common goal is to set up a balance between the principles of Islam and a secular structure and to ensure equality and justice among people.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, the concepts of state understanding and secularism in the Islamic world are widely considered as complex and controversial topics. Issues such as the role of Islam in government administration, ensuring equality and justice among citizens, and the influence of religious beliefs on government management are some of the topics that bring different opinions and debates in the Islamic world.

However, the common goal of these debates is to promote equality and justice among people and to set up a balance between the principles of Islam and a secular structure. The implementation of secularism in modern Islamic states can be seen because of efforts to achieve this balance. Despite the varying views on the concepts of state understanding and secularism in the Islamic world, the shared aim is to promote justice and equality among people. In line with this aim, Islamic states prioritize the implementation of secularism.

In summary, the concepts of state understanding and secularism in the Islamic world can be seen because of attempts to set up a balance between the principles of Islam and a secular structure, and the aim is to promote equality and justice among people.

Since Islam is a religion that deals with religious and social life together, state and society relations are also at the center of Islam. Different state structures have appeared in different periods throughout the history of Islam, and Islamic states have undergone changes and evolved from traditional management understandings to modern states.

In Islam, the state is an institution that must be governed by the provisions of Islam. The purpose of the state is to ensure the security and welfare of the society, to set up justice and to encourage the people to live by Islamic teachings. A state governed by the application of the basic principles and provisions of Islam is thought to increase the welfare of the people and to be governed fairly. This policy was a response to the expansion of public activity in these areas during this time. Activities and organizations based on religious beliefs that conduct these activities are also subject to the same strict control as their non-religious counterparts. Religious identity was respected by legislation; however, over time, a considerable number of

CURRENT SCIENCE

organizations running in key sectors such as education and health "closed" to the state. In Dutch culture, religious affiliation has historically played a key role in the formation of social groups and organizations. This social self-organization was also a chance for some sects to "liberate" themselves socio-economically, and this is one of the reasons they did so. This more general pattern of social organization along sectarian lines came to be described as the "colonization" of Dutch society, as we have just discussed. It included, among others, such formations as newspapers, mass media associations, youth groups, employers' and workers' organizations, and entertainment organizations such as football clubs. After the end of the Second World War, there was pressure to create a social welfare state, which resulted in decolonization. As a result, the religious identity of many already existing organizations has become less clear, with the possible exception being organizations that have a significant educational focus and work with younger children, such as primary schools. The Dutch Constitution does not set up a hierarchy of rights; instead, it ensures that all fundamental rights are protected on an equal basis. To address the issue at hand, it is necessary to strike a balance between these rights and horizontal links, i.e., when it comes to interactions in the private sector. This must be done by law and by law. This is primarily the responsibility of the parliamentary legislature, as the courts do not have the power to evaluate the lawfulness of laws passed by the parliamentary legislature.

Secularism, on the other hand, means the separation of religion and politics of the state. In a secular state, religion and state affairs are separated from each other, and there is no understanding of administration based on any religion or belief. The concept of secularism has developed as a part of the modern state understanding and is practiced in many countries of the world. However, in certain situations, courts are obliged to apply and interpret the law. In addition, they have the authority to evaluate such laws according to whether they follow the requirements of directly applicable international agreements or the decisions of public international organizations. Currently, a State Committee has been formed to advise on several constitutional issues. One of these issues is the appropriateness of a preface and, if desired, the possible content of the preface.

The concept of secularism in the Islamic world has led to different interpretations. Some Islamic scholars reject secularism as it is incompatible with the basic principles of Islam. Others argue that a secular state understanding is possible by the basic principles of Islam.

As a result, the issue of state and secularism in Islam causes different interpretations and discussions. However, it is accepted that a state governed by the application of the basic principles and provisions of Islam can increase the welfare of the people and be governed fairly. In addition, the concept of secularism, which is included in the understanding of the modern state, can be applied in harmony with the basic principles of Islam. It should not be forgotten that the views of different Islamic scholars should be respected on this issue and the issue will continue to be discussed.

11. References

- Akan M. (2017b). "Diversité: challenging or constituting Laicité?" *Fr. Cult. Stud.* 28, 123–137. 10.1177/0957155816678590
- Alkan, Türker. "The National Salvation Party in Turkey." In *Islam and Politics in the Modern Middle East*, edited by Metin Heper and Raphael Israeli. London: Croom Helm, 1984,
- Asad T. (1993). *Genealogies of Religion: Discipline and Reasons of Power in Christianity and Islam*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Asad T. (2003). *Formations of the Secular: Christianity, Islam, Modernity*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Aydın, M. (1995). Türkiye’de Din-Devlet İlişkisi ve Laiklik. *Köprü Dergisi*, 51, 1-3.
- Barkey K. (2008). *Empire of Difference: The Ottomans in Comparative Perspective*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Berkes, Niyazi. *The Development of Secularism in Turkey*. Montreal: McGill University Development, edited by Lucian W. Pye and Sydney Verba. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1965), pp. 171–198.
- Ergil, D. (1989). Laiklik Üzerine Düşünceler:" Türkiye Örneği". *Ankara Üniversitesi SBF Dergisi*, 44(03).
- Foundation, March 2010.
- GAM 15.7.2005. 'Clarity Needed to Reach Peace Agreement', State of Aceh, Ministry of Information, Norsborg, Sweden.
- Gülalp, Haldun. "Globalization and Political Islam: The Social Bases of Turkey's Welfare
- Gündüz, Ş. (2010). Evrensel Dinin Millileştirilmesi: Anglikanizm ve Türk İslamı. *Milel ve Nihal*, 7(3), 9-38.

- Harsono, A. 2001. 'Aceh Secession Hobbled by Internal Strife', *The American Reporter*. 14 February 2001.
- Hulst, W. 1991 (trans: ASNLF). 'From Now On, It Is Not Just Free Aceh But Free Sumatra!', *NRC Handelsblad*. 1 June 1991.
- ICG 2003. *Jema'ah Islamiyah in Southeast Asia: Damaged but Still Dangerous* Jakarta and Brussels, 26 August 2003.
- Kell, T. 1995. *The Roots of Acehese Rebellion* Cornell Modern Indonesia Project, Ithaca, NY.
- Loeb, E. 1974 (1935) *Sumatra: Its History and People* Oxford University Press, London.
- Manji, I. *The Trouble With Islam Today: A Muslim's Call for Reform in Her Faith*. New York: Saint Martin's Griffin, 2005.
- Marsden, W. 1975 (1811) *The History of Sumatra*, 3rd ed. Oxford University Press, Kuala Lumpur.
- Ortaylı, İ. (1997). Osmanlı Devletinde Laiklik ve Hukukun Romanizasyonu. *Erdem*, 9(27), 1201-1208.
- Özdağ, M. (1988). Türklük, İslamiyet, Laiklik. *Istanbul Journal of Sociological Studies*, (22), 87-114.
- Party." *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 33 (2001): 433–448. Rustow, Dankwart. "Turkey: The Modernity of Tradition." In *Political Culture and Political* pp. 79–102. Press, 1964.
- Rajab, T. *Re-Programming British Muslims – A Study of the Islam Channel*. London: Quilliam
- Roy, O. *Holy Ignorance*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2010.
- Roy, O. *Secularism Confronts Islam*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2007.
- State. New York: I. B. Tauris, 1991
- Akan M. (2017a). *Politics of Secularism: Religion, Diversity, and Institutional Change in France and Turkey*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Tapper, Richard, ed. *Islam in Modern Turkey: Religion, Politics and Literature in a Secular*
- Yilmaz, I. (2013). *Türkiye'de Yeni Anayasa Tartışmaları: Din Özgürlüğü ve İslama Ters Düşmeyen Laik Devlet Üzerine Bir Yorum Denemesi* (New Constitution Debate in

CURRENT SCIENCE

Turkey: Religious Freedom and A Secular Constitution Compatible with Islam).
Available at SSRN 2218393.